

Performance of biodegradable active packaging in the preservation of fresh-cut fruits: A systematic review

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Abstract: Fresh-cutting fruits is a common practice in markets and households, but their short shelf life is a challenge to face. Active packaging is a prominent strategy for extending food shelf life. A systematic review was conducted following the PRISMA guidelines to explore the performance and materials used in biodegradable active packaging for fresh-cut fruits. Thirteen studies were included from a search performed in August 2023 on Scopus and Web of Science databases. Only research articles in English on biodegradable active films tested on cut fruits were selected. Polysaccharides were the most employed polymer for film matrix development (87.5%). Antioxidant and antibrowning activity were the most developed properties for the active films (62.5%). Plant extracts and essential oils were the most employed active agents for materials designs (56.3%). And fresh-cut apples are the main tested fruit (56.3%). Each configuration exhibited characteristic performance. In addition, there is a diversity of experimental designs for evaluating the shelf-life improvement. In each case, shelf-life extension was successfully achieved. The findings show that storage design, fruit, and materials configuration can achieve different shelf-life extension performance. This lack of standardization in shelf-life designs makes it difficult to disclose the better active packaging configurations.

Keywords: Fresh-cut fruits; active packaging; shelf life; biodegradable; films

1. Introduction

Fresh-cut fruits are a common presentation due to their easy handling and convenient accessibility for households and consumers, which have turned their attention to ready-to-eat foods [1,2]. However, preserving them presents a challenge that households and markets must address. Nutrient loss and microbial spoilage are common occurrences in fresh fruits following peeling and cutting [3]. Processing, such as cutting, triggers an increase in respiration rates and biochemical responses that end in enzymatic browning [4]. Fresh-cutting also increases susceptibility to deterioration, microbial spoilage, and oxidation due to the loss of the natural barrier provided by the peel and tissue damage [1]. These factors contribute to a reduction in the fruit's shelf life, generally between 1 and 3 days, and quality loss [3–5]. Short shelf life is one of the main causes of food loss and waste across the globe. The shelf life of fruits is closely related to physiological, environmental, and storage conditions.

Food packaging is a prominent alternative since one of its objectives is to extend the food shelf life providing barrier protection against external factors such as moisture, microbes, and physical damage [6]. Further, researchers have focused on active packaging development. Active packaging is a food protection and shelf-life extension strategy. It interacts with the inner atmosphere by releasing active components (antioxidants or antimicrobials) or scavenging undesirable gases (oxygen or ethylene) to prevent food spoilage and promote shelf-life extension [7].

The environmental implications of petroleum-based plastics are considerable, largely due to their processability, emissions, and non-degradability [8,9]. Consequently, the development of renewable or biobased materials is being encouraged [9]. Polysaccharides, proteins, and lipids are food packaging material alternatives [10]. Renewability, non-toxicity, abundance, and degradability are some of the advantages of biobased plastics [10,11].

As there are so many raw materials and configurations, different properties and performances have been achieved, and these properties are difficult to disclose in general terms. Novel packaging films' performance is characterized by their barrier, temperature, mechanical, flexible, and active properties, which are related to proper food packaging application, quality preservation, or shelf-life extension [12]. Shelf-life tests are important for active packaging evaluation. In many cases, studies on active packaging development have employed this test to relate the behavior of active packaging configurations to potential applications. Characterizing physiological (weight loss, firmness, color, acidity, soluble solids), decay spoilage (bacterial or mold counts) and shelf life achieved of tested foods.

Since the shelf-life test is very relevant and assumes an important role in defining the success of packaging materials, the reported results in the active packaging literature should be explored and disclosed. This information contributes to the diversification and development of new and effective active packaging materials. Thus, the objective of this review is to relate the performance of biodegradable active packaging films in the shelf-life tests of fresh-cut fruits in publications of the last 10 years.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Review Design and Eligibility Criteria

This systematic review was made using PRISMA guideline [13]. The methodology consisted of searching, identifying, and analyzing studies from the active packaging literature related to biodegradable films tested on fresh-cut fruits. The information sources were the scientific databases, Scopus, and Web of Science. The selection of studies was done using as inclusion criteria: 1. Only research articles, 2. Publications from 2013 to 2024, 3. Active packaging material, 4. Biodegradable materials. As exclusion criteria: 1. Reviews and book chapters, 2. Publications in other languages than English, 3. No film type materials, 4. Active packaging under modified atmosphere conditions, 5. Studies performed shelf-life tests of food different to cut fruits.

2.2. Information Sources and Search Strategy

The reviewed information was obtained from the scientific databases Scopus, and Web of Science. The search was performed in July 2024. The search strategy was developed using a keyword and Boolean query. The query "(All Fields) [food packaging films AND fruit* AND biodegradable]" filters: (Publication years) [2013-2023] (Document types) [Article] was used in Web of Science. The query "(All fields) ["food packaging films" AND "cut fruit*" AND biodegradable]" filters: (Years) [2013-2023] was used in Scopus.

2.3. Study Selection Process

The reference manager web application Rayyan was used for article management. The process started with the revision of the title and abstracts of each study by three independent researchers (OTR, MFV and LED). The three researchers then collaboratively reviewed the studies with conflicts (two approved and one refused). The approved studies were fully read and filtered out again of those that did not meet the inclusion criteria.

2.4. Data Collection

To collect data, a database form was developed and used to summarize the following information: article title, corresponding author name and country, year of publication, journal name, raw materials for film synthesis, active substances, evaluated activities, prepared fruit samples, shelf-life evaluation, and film characterization.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Main Results

A total of 577 articles were identified during the search stage, including 261 from Scopus and 316 from Web of Science. From these, 10 articles were removed as duplicates. After screening the remaining articles, 356 were excluded. The main reasons for exclusion were no shelf-life tests on methodology or food other than fruits, review type articles, overviews, and chapters.

Of the 211 potentially eligible articles, 195 did not meet the inclusion criteria as they had different focus on shelf-life test like packaging no fresh-cut fruits, for example, bananas [14], strawberries [15], grapes [16], mangoes [17], among others. And fruit samples coated by immersion [18] or spraying [19] instead of wrapping them on a film. Thus, 16 studies were included for data collection (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram [20].

A first consideration is the location of the study, for which the country of affiliation of the corresponding author was selected. In general, 9 countries contributed publications for active packaging literature. It is worth noting that India (31.3%) and China (18.8%) have advanced in this research field (Fig. 2A). This may be due to growing interest in using eco-friendly materials for food packaging and reducing food loss and waste. These concerns could be particularly relevant in highly industrialized, populated, and biodiverse countries. Governments, entities, and organizations recognize that eco-friendly packaging is of utmost importance in the future [21]. The increase in publication production is also noted. The last 5 years have overcome more than half (81.3%) of articles (Fig. 2B). Complementary, 18.8% of the studies were from Europe, 12.5% from Africa, and 6.3% from America.

Figure 2. A) Geographical distribution of research. B) Publications distribution over years.

3.2. Main Polymers for Active Packaging

Petroleum-based plastics used in food packaging have raised several concerns about their environmental impact. As they are single-use and contribute significantly to waste. This has led researchers to explore the development of biodegradable and low-cost materials.

There are several strategies and configurations for biodegradable plastics film fabrication. Generally, the use of residual biological mass has gained attention for this issue. The most common and important polymers employed as raw materials are polysaccharides and proteins [22]. On the other hand, advances in polymer synthesis have provided biodegradable polymers like polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), poly(butylene-adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT), and polycaprolactone (PCL).

Polysaccharides are some of the most employed due to their abundance (some as by-products of agricultural industry), biocompatibility, and biodegradability. Of the articles included, 87.5% employed them as materials for

fabricating polymer matrices. They were followed by synthetic biodegradable polymers and then proteins for film packaging fabrication. Composites of different polysaccharides, polysaccharides with proteins or polysaccharides with aliphatic polyesters are common strategies for fabricating film matrices with major capabilities. Therefore, most of the studies have considered making composites as the main strategy to develop active packaging films.

Chitosan and cellulose derivatives are among the most used polysaccharides, appearing as raw materials in 31.3% of the studies. Chitosan is a frequently used alternative as it is highly abundant and has antimicrobial activity. This activity is achieved as microbes cell wall deteriorate by the negative-positive reaction with the polymer [23]. The crystalline structure of cellulose allows for materials with high stiffness, durability, and thermal stability [23]. Starch closely follows with 12.5% of studies. Starch odorless, colorless, chemical inertness, and film-forming abilities are some of the reasons for its wide utilization [24]. These polymers are low-cost and suitable carriers for different active substances [23].

Against, synthetic biodegradable polymers were the second most employed materials in investigations, following polysaccharides. Synthetic biodegradable polymers have been found to be nontoxic, biocompatible, and to exhibit good processability [25]. These classes of raw polymer material were considered in 37.5% of the studies, mainly blended with natural polymers. As shown in this review, blends of polysaccharides with synthetic polymers are common strategies to reinforce mechanical properties, like tensile strength, elongation at break and, Young modulus [26], improve processability, like spinnability in the case of polysaccharides [26], and reduce manufacturing costs in the case of synthetic polymers [27].

Over time, protein gelatin has been a prevalent raw material in many applications, like in food and pharmaceutical industries. It is widely used because of its film-forming capacity, transparency, elasticity, and protective properties against light and temperature [28]. Nearly all vegetable proteins, such as wheat gluten, corn zein, and soy protein among others, have found their way into food packaging applications [29]. In total, 18.8% of the articles employed them, so they were the less common of raw materials.

Despite chitosan, any other polymer used in film packaging acts as a passive barrier. Thus, to promote shelf-life extension, bioactive substances must be incorporated on polymer matrices.

3.3. Active Principles

Active packaging for fresh-cut fruits typically provides antioxidant, antibrowning, or antimicrobial properties. Antioxidant activity is achieved by the removal of free radicals accepted for scavenger molecules, such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and terpenes, which have radical scavenging capabilities [30,31]. This is the main activity to develop active packaging for fresh-cut fruits, and this was reported in 62.5% of the studies.

Antibrowning activity is a major advantage for quality maintenance in fresh-cut products. Some ways to prevent browning are to inhibit the enzymatic action of polyphenol oxidase (PPO) by creating an oxygen barrier or scavenger capacity of the active packaging [32]. Thus, 62.5% of studies characterized this activity as a further potential capacity of films.

Antibacterial activity has important repercussions and is mainly related to quality conservation and food security. Fresh-cut fruits provide favorable environments for microbial growth due to nutrients and surface area exposure, moisture loss and browning [33–35]. Given consumer concerns, active packaging may offer a viable alternative to chemical preservative-based additives [36]. According to this, 50% of the studies promoted and evaluated this activity. Only one study focused on inhibiting fungi, while the others focused on inhibiting bacterial strains.

Further, active packaging with both antioxidant and antimicrobial activities has the potential to grow. Only 31.3% of the studies searched for these two properties at once. Similarly, a wide variety of natural substances have been proposed. Plant extracts are the most common source of bioactive components. The mixture of phenolic components in plant extracts promotes antioxidant and antibacterial properties. Nonetheless, their incorporation into polymer matrices has led to mechanical, physicochemical, and barrier modifications [37].

With 56.3% occurrence, plant extracts and essential oils are the main active agents employed for active packaging. These highly biologically active agents. Principally composed of phenolic and flavonoid compounds, which promote antioxidant and antibacterial activity, acting as scavengers of free radicals and modifying cell membranes or DNA of bacteria's [38].

3.4. Film fabrication procedures

Three distinct manufacturing procedures have been employed for the production of films, namely electrospinning, extrusion, and casting. These procedures are based on the capacity of polymers to be electrospun, extruded, and cast, respectively. All of the aforementioned methods are typically initiated with polymer solution mixtures, comprising a combination of polymers and fillers. The solution casting method is the most prevalent due to its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, large-scale production of biodegradable films [39], and suitability for active packaging based on thermosensitive molecules.

As previously stated, most methodologies entail the incorporation of active substances prior to the formation of the polymeric matrix, being in fact fillers. Consequently, experimental film design has been conceptualized as a means of assessing the impact of augmented quantities of active substances, such as fillers, on the characteristics and functionality of packaging films. For instance, an increase in the proportion of filler results in a deterioration of the mechanical properties of the film, due to the occurrence of phase separation, failure points, or the presence of discontinuities in the polymer matrix.

Deposition by coating or immersing seemed to be a novel approach that hasn't been widely explored. In fact, only one article employed this with not significant changes in the mechanical performance [40].

3.5. Main Tested Fresh-cut Fruits

Fresh-cut fruit has advantages in terms of ease handling and manipulation for households; these products are ready to use and consume and are easier to store on shelves and in refrigerators, especially useful for bulky fruits like watermelon and melon. In this review, it was observed that 8 types of fresh-cut fruits were tested in storage with active packaging. Of these, apples seem to be the most relevant, as they were the focus of 56.3% of the studies. The rest of the studies validated fresh-cut watermelons (2 articles), bananas (1 article), tomatoes (1 article), kiwis (1 article), melons (1 article), mangoes (1 article), strawberries (1 article), durians (1 article), and pomegranate (1 article).

Despite their easy handling, fresh cutting has a negative impact on fruit quality. Physiological, chemical, and sensory changes occur quickly, and some are catalyzed by enzymes like the polyphenol oxidase [41]. Freshly cut apples become rapidly oxidized and browned due to the exposure of polyphenol oxidase to the environment and softened due to the hydrolysis of pectin [42]. The rate and propensity to oxidation and browning of fresh-cut apples makes them the primary means of validating the performance of active packaging [43].

In general, the methods for preparing samples for shelf-life testing involve selecting fruits based on their healthy appearance, uniformity in size and stage of ripeness, and the absence of physical and microbial damage. The fruits are then washed with distilled water and, in some cases, decontaminated with sodium hypochlorite to remove dirt and sanitize them. Further, fruits are peeled and cut into slices or cubes. Finally, the fruits are packed in the active films developed by the study and subjected to defined temperature and humidity conditions for storage. The test time ranges from 6 hours to 14 days.

3.6. Performance of Active Packaging Films

Biodegradable active packaging exhibits various performances (table 1). Each study has its own characteristic experimental design, which makes the results difficult to compare with each other.

Table 1. Main performance of the included studies on shelf-life extension.

Polymer Matrix	Fillers Employed	Films manufacturing method	Fresh-cut Fruits	Main Results	Positive points	Negative points	Author and year of Publication
Polybutylene succinate (PBS)	Extra virgin olive oil (PBS/EVO 1, 2, 3%wt) or coconut oil (PBS/CO 1, 2, 3%wt)	The polymer-filler mixture was extruded into pellets and then blown into film.	Apples and Kiwi halves in direct contact with the developed films stored for 12 days.	The shelf life of the fruits was monitored for 12 days. PBS (passive) and PBS/CO (active) films maintained the quality of fruits for nearly 3 days. PBS/EVO films (active) were shown to inhibit fungal spoilage in fruits for a further 5 days with a superior performance to that of PBS and PBS/CO films. Specially, PBS/3%EVO showed the better performance. Thus, PBS/EVO films promote a shelf life of fruits of nearly 8 days.	The water resistance is enhanced due to the increased hydrophobicity provided by oils. PBS/EVO films have the overall higher elongation at break (119.8% for 3%EVO).	Tensile strength (22.5 MPa pristine PBS) is reduced by the addition of oils due to phase separation occurrence.	Barrino et al, 2023 [44]
Zein and Chitosan Glycerol or PEG400 plasticizers	---	Chitosan or Zein film-forming solutions were casted into film.	Apples cubes placed in containers covered with the developed films. Stored at 30°C and 50% RH for 24 hours.	Both chitosan and zein films showed antioxidant capabilities. However, the performance of the zein films (near 68% DPPH assay) was higher than that of the chitosan film (near 20%). After 24 hours, the packaging performance in terms of fruit color is not significantly different between biopolymers and commercial PVC films. However, in terms of weight loss, PVC behaves better with close to 3%, then zein films with close to 10%, and chitosan films with 17%.	Acceptable mechanical properties of PEG-400 plasticizer formulations. Chitosan/50%PEG400 (TS >50 MPa and EAB >40%) superior overall performance.	Increased swelling, moisture content, and water-vapor permeability due to lower hydrophobicity.	Bharathi et al, 2020 [43]
Chitosan (1.5%w/v) /polyethylene glycol (PEG 400) (50% w/w)	Anacardic acid (5, 10, 15 mg/100 mL)	The film-forming solution was dried using a conductive hydro drying setup.	Apple slices (3x1.7x1.5 cm) wrapped on films and stored for 6 hours. No other storage conditions were reported.	Film highest antioxidant activity was 28.4% (DPPH assay) for 15 mg treatment. Furthermore, individually, chitosan and anacardic acid have proven antimicrobial activity. After 6 hours, the films showed capacities for browning reaction inhibition (browning index near 4) and weight loss control (between 15% and 20%).	No significant changes are observed in the mechanical properties (TS 0.029 MPa, EAB 119%). Proper soil biodegradability developed.	Despite the hydrophobicity of anacardic acid, films exhibit high water solubility.	Preethi et al, 2021 [45]

Chitosan	Vanillin nanoparticles	Chitosan solution was casted into film and then immersed in the vanillin NP solution for 5 minutes.	Watermelons, melons, and strawberries cut in cylindrical plugs (2.5 cm diameter, 3 cm length), placed on square films and stored in polyethylene terephthalate containers for: 9 days at 10°C for watermelons and 12 days at 8°C for melons and strawberries.	Antimicrobial effects against gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria are based on chitosan activity. A significant reduction in CFU quantification (~6log) was achieved. No effect from vanillin nanoparticles has been reported. Antibiofilm properties can be achieved only in E. coli when vanillin nanoparticles are incorporated into the chitosan polymer. With active packaging, microbial inhibition was significantly improved, remaining below the acceptability thresholds 4 days further than control (not packed). Chitosan packaging yields approximately 4.5 bacterial and 2 mold and yeast counts (log CFU/g) on watermelon after 9 days of storage. Near 7.7 bacterial and 6 mold-yeast counts (log CFU/g) on melons after 12 days. Furthermore, nearly 7 bacterial and 6.5 mold-yeast counts (log CFU/g) were detected in strawberries after 12 days. The incorporation of vanillin lowered these values to near; 4 and 0 (watermelon), 5.5 and 4 (melon), 5.7 and 5 (strawberries), and bacterial and mold-yeast counts (log CFU/g), respectively.	Films are thermally resistant (11% mass loss) until 200 °C.	Mechanical properties and water vapor permeability with further improvement (TS 24.24 MPa and EAB of 24.25%).	Buslovich et al, 2018 [40]
Poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate)(32-49%wt)/Starch (32-49%wt) Glycerol (16%wt) plasticizer	Nanocellulose (0.45%wt), citric acid (0.4 and 0.8%wt), and annatto (0.8%wt)	The polymer-filler mixture was extruded into pellets and then extruded into films.	Mango pieces (2 cm x 2 cm ²) in 15 cm x 20 cm film turned into a bag and stored at 5°C, RH between 85 and 90% for 14 days.	The shelf-life performance of the formulations was comparable to that of commercial PVC films. The moisture content of the fruit remained near 90% for 7 days and near 80% on day 14. The absence of mold and yeast indicates the possible antimicrobial activity of annatto.	Slight improvement in the water-vapor barrier capability.	Small reduction (<6.65 MPa) in the tensile strength in films with fillers due to some incompatibilities with polymer matrix.	Leal et al, 2019 [27]

Starch (6%w/v) Glycerol (2%v/v)	Liposome: Vitamin C capsules (0.1%w/v)	The film-forming solution of gelatinized starch/glycerol and VC capsules was casted into films.	Apple pieces (1cm width x 2.5 cm diameter) wrapped in the films and stored at different pH (4 and 7) and temperatures (20, 25 and 37°C)	The active film can release vitamin C into packaged fruit for 3 to 4 hours. Low pH and higher temperatures show faster release. Liposome encapsulation modified the diffusivity, which helped to control the release. Thus, having prolonged activity.	Antioxidant capabilities provided by vitamin C.	No other information about films' characteristics.	Khuntia et al, 2022 [46]
Gelatin (3% w/v) Glycerol plasticizer (0.6% w/v) Tween 20 emulsifier (0.018% w/v)	Durian leaf extract (0.2 and 0.5 %w/v)	The film-forming solution was casted into films.	Durian portions are wrapped in films and stored at 4°C for 4 weeks.	Durian leaf extract promoted antioxidant activity on gelatin films. The films loaded with 0.5% extract exhibited 0.44 and 3.445 mg/mL Trolox Equivalent per 100 mg of film in the DPPH and FRAP assays, respectively. Durian leaf extract modified the performance of the gelatin film, reducing fruit weight loss to 27%, for the 0.2% loaded gelatin film, and 33 % for the 0.5% loaded gelatin film after 4 weeks. The commercial film (control) behaved slightly better with 17%. No significant differences were observed in the physical changes of fruit packed with commercial or gelatin-leaf extract films.	Strong antioxidant capabilities.	The water vapor barrier was not improved as expected. No other film characteristic is characterized.	Joanne Kam et al, 2018 [47]
Sodium alginate(1%w/v) /carboxymethyl cellulose (1%w/v) Glycerol (0.02%w/v) CaCl ₂ and Citric acid crosslinkers (0.2%w/v)	Shallot onion peel extract (0.2-0.5%w/v) Shallot onion stalk extract (0.2-0.5%w/v)	The film-forming solution was casted into films.	Apple slices wrapped in the developed films and stored in polypropylene trays for 12 days at 4°C.	Sodium alginate/carboxymethyl cellulose films exhibited antioxidant activity provided by shallot onion extracts. Peel extracts at 0.5% in film provided the better overall performance nearly 92.28% and 78.82% radical scavenging ability in the DPPH and ABTS assays, respectively. After 12 days of storage, apple browning was controlled.	Proper water resistance and barrier to vapor and oxygen due to adequate polyphenol and matrix interactions.	Significant change in appearance turning to red the color of films.	Thivya et al, 2021 [48]

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) (8%w/v)/Kefiran (6%w/v)/Polycaprolactone (PCL) (15%w/v)	Flexirubin pigment (15%wt)	Double layered film obtained by electrospinning. Inner layer Kefiran:PVA (1:2). Outer layer PCL.	Apple slices wrapped in the developed films in a 12-hour storage. No other storage conditions were reported.	The incorporation of kefiran and flexirubin enhances the antioxidant capacity. A 41.03% ABTS test can be achieved. Apple slices packed with this film can achieve a maximum weight loss of 4.5%.	No significant changes occur in mechanical properties (TS 3.45MPa and EAB 8.55%) and porosity with flexirubin incorporation.	High water transmission due to low hydrophobicity development or high porosity.	F. A. Amorim et al, 2022 [26]
Chitosan (65%wt) Glycerol (15%wt)	Kaolinite clay (10%wt) and Ficus leaf extract (10%wt)	The film-forming solution was casted into films.	Apple pieces wrapped in the developed films and stored in ambient conditions for 24 hours.	Ficus leaf extract can enhance the antioxidant activity of chitosan films from nearly 20% to 60% for free radicals scavenging in DPPH assays at a 10 mg/mL film equivalent. The active films show great performance in preserving the fruit for 24 hours. The performance in terms of weight loss improved from nearly 27% in the pristine chitosan film to nearly 15% in the chitosan film with fillers. The color and phenolic content remained like those of fresh fruit.	Proper water resistance as well as barrier capacity due to the crystallinity and hydrophobicity of the material. UV light barrier protection gain. Thermal resistance (near 20% mass loss) up to 240°C and superior mechanical properties (TS 21.08MPa and EAB 33.35%).	Green color gain in the films due to extracts incorporation.	El Mouzahim et al, 2023 [49]
Cellulose acetate thermoplastic (CAT)	Potassium sorbate in layered double hydroxide (LDH-sorbate) (1.25, 2.5, and 5%wt)	The composite mixture was extruded into bags.	Pomegranate arils stored in bags from the developed films at 8°C and 20°C for 10 days.	The inclusion of sorbate in the films promotes a sustainable release of active particles. LDH-sorbate cellulose films release active substances after 120 days. Physiological deterioration in aril was effectively delayed and improved from 10% and 25% in Cat and polyethylene film packaging, respectively, to 5% deterioration in composite LDH-sorbate-CAT packaging after the 10 days storage.	Thermal resistance (30% mass loss) up to near 295°C.	Up to 5%wt concentration tensile strength decreased (20MPa). The elongation at break was significantly decreased (<9%) due to discontinuities in the polymer matrix.	Oliviero et al, 2023 [9]

Agar (1.6% w/v)/carrageenan (0.2% w/v) Glycerol (0.6% w/v)	Nisin (0.2, 0.24, 0.28, 0.32 and 0.36% w/v)	The film-forming solution was casted into films.	Watermelon (2x2 cm squares) stored in plastic bowls covered with the developed films at 90% RH for 3 days at 4°C, and 1 day at 20°C.	The active film shows the antibacterial activity of nisin on in vitro assays. Inhibition circle width increased from 0 mm in 0% nisin content to nearly 4 mm against <i>S. aureus</i> and nearly 2 mm against <i>L. monocytogenes</i> in 0.36% nisin film. After 15 days of storage at 4°C, the cut watermelon exhibited 2.4% weight loss. Bacterial spoilage can be slowed down for a few days. And quality parameters such as soluble solids, hardness, titratable acids, and vitamin c content can be better maintained in comparison with PE films.	This configuration exhibited favorable mechanical properties at 20% RH (TS>20 MPa and EAB > 15%).	Low oxygen and air barrier capacity due to phase separation when nisin was incorporated. Low mechanical performance at 90%RH.	Song et al, 2023 [22]
Pectin (3%w/v)/ polyethylene glycol (PEG) (25% w/w pectin)	Grapefruit methanolic extract (0.04% w/w) and maltodextrin encapsulated lemon extract (0.04% w/w)	The film-forming solution was casted and spread into films with a film applicator.	Cherry Tomatoes are cut in halves wrapped with active films and stored in polystyrene boxes at 4 °C for 6 days.	Each citric-based material has antioxidant capabilities (Pectin, grapefruit extract and lemon extract), which increase the total phenolic content of the film. The maximum antioxidant activity is obtained when all three are present (84.73 DPPH assay). Incorporating citric extracts achieved proven antibacterial activity against <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. enteritidis</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , and <i>K. pneumoniae</i> . Packaging treatment of artificially contaminated (with <i>E. coli</i>) cherry tomatoes stored at 6°C demonstrated the antibacterial activity of the active films, decreasing the original count population of 5.28 Log CFU/g to 3.69 Log CFU/g on the 6th day.	The films have UV-light barrier capacity. Thermal stability (near 16% mass loss) under temperature ranges of 200-250 °C. Flexibility over 10%EAB and biodegradability.	Low water solubility resistance is due to abundant hydrophilic groups.	Khalil et al, 2023 [50]

Chitosan (2%w/v) /Guar gum (no reported fraction)	Watermelon rind extract (1, 2, and 4%wt)	The film-forming solution was casted into films.	Banana (2 cm height slices) packaged in two 12x12cm sealed films into bags. Storage for 5 days; no other conditions reported.	Chitosan/guar gum films exhibited 20% DPPH scavenging activity. The watermelon rind extract increased the performance by up to 84%. Both chitosan and the natural extract provided the film antibacterial activity being effective against <i>E. coli</i> and <i>S. aureus</i> pathogens. By measuring the inhibition zone in agar, the inclusion of watermelon rind extract increased from 10 mm to nearly 16 mm. The inclusion of extracts improved the shelf-life performance of the fruit, as measured by color, firmness, weight loss, soluble solid content, and sensory evaluation. Additionally, the active packaging developed maintained the appearance of the fruit for two days more than the control polymer, from 2 to 4 days.	The material exhibits thermal resistance (near 30% mass loss) up to 250 °C. Additionally, it has developed UV-light barrier capacity. And improved tensile strength (>34.23 MPa)	Low elongation at break (below 5.5%) due to the presence of failure points and disturbed matrix structure. Additionally, the water vapor barrier requires stronger hydrophobicity.	Wang et al, 2023 [51]
Soy protein isolate (SPI) (5%wt)/ Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) (2%wt) Glycerol (3%wt)	Cinnamon and <i>Litsea cubeba</i> essential oils in polydopamine nanocapsules (0.125, 0.25, 0.5, and 1%wt)	The film-forming solution was casted into films.	Apple pieces (1 cm x 1cm ²) placed in sterile cups covered with the developed films and stored at 4°C.	SPI-CMC film exhibited 2.4% in DPPH and 18.7% in ABTS assays. The addition of essential oil nanocapsules significantly improved antioxidant activity to values near 66.6% and 98.6% in the DPPH and ABTS assays, respectively, for the 1%wt nanocapsules formulation. Antibacterial activity was developed due to essential oil release being effective against <i>E. coli</i> and <i>S. aureus</i> bacteria. Films delayed browning and deterioration of cut apples, improving from 12 hours of shelf life in control films to more than 24 hours in 1%wt essential oil capsule films.	The thermal resistance of the materials was between 15% and 31% mass loss until 200°C. 0.5%wt exhibits the better mechanical performance (TS 8MPa, EAB 150%). 1%wt exhibit the better hydrophobicity (107° CA). Generally the water vapor barrier performance. In addition, the material provides 100% UV protection.	The color darkened brown. The swelling ratio increased due to the high porosity of the films.	Wang et al, 2023 [52]

Methylcellulose (M) (2%w/v)/ Glutaraldehyde (G) crosslinker (10 mL, 2%)	Noni leaf extract (20 mL, 0.005%w/v)	The film-forming solution was casted into films.	Apple syrup and slices covered with the films and stored at room temperature for 120 hours.	The inclusion of noni leaf extract promoted antibacterial activity from 11 mm in pristine film to 15 mm in gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria and fungi. Furthermore, antioxidant performance was improved from 20.1% and 28.9% in the DPPH and ABTS assays, respectively, to 93.1% and 90.5%. Browning, pH loss, and weight loss were effectively delayed for 120 hours. In addition, the bioactivity of apples was significantly maintained, indicating they had proper quality after storage.	The tensile strength was also improved (41.8 MPa). Furthermore, the hydrophobicity of the material increased (90.3° CA), enhancing its vapor barrier properties.	The elongation at break decreased slightly because of reduced chain mobility due to the incorporation of noni leaf extract.	Eelager et al, 2024 [53]
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3.7. Antioxidant Advantages

From all the studies, it can be observed that antioxidant packaging films have an advantage in maintaining aspect and sensory quality. Oxidation processes affect the quality of perishable foods, which can be expressed by their color, flavor, and texture deterioration [54]. In fresh-cut fruits, enzymatic browning and oxidation of substrates shorten their shelf-life. One of the most common antibrowning agents is essential oils [55]. Therefore, we appreciate the researcher's interest in natural extracts. Briefly, all studies have confirmed that antioxidant active packaging prolongs the shelf life of fresh-cut fruits. Generally, DPPH and ABTS assays have become the mandatory tests for antioxidant capacity measurement in the antioxidant active packaging. This may be due to the sensitivity and obtention of quantifiable results.

3.8. Antibacterial Advantages

Microbial contamination often causes premature spoilage of food, compromising the quality and safety of food products [56,57]. Thus, antimicrobial packaging acts as a shelf-life extension and food security strategy. The results demonstrate that active substances can promote bacterial inhibition when incorporated into polymer matrices. Antimicrobial active packaging is effective in controlling microbial growth (bacteria and fungi) [57]. Additionally, the antibacterial active packaging prolongs the shelf life of fresh cut fruits.

3.9. Positive characteristics in active packaging films

Furthermore, there is a necessity for continued advancement in the development of biodegradable packaging films. While active properties may serve as a support, it is essential that mechanical, barrier, and thermal properties be subjected to rigorous analysis to ensure that these developments are competitive against commercial polymers. In positive aspect, films with UV-light barrier are remarkable designs. Phenols functional groups provide favorable sites for ultraviolet (UV) absorbance [50]. UV protection is desirable to mitigate appearance deterioration and nutrient degradation.

In all cases, thermal resistance up to high temperatures (over 100°C) are promising results. Thus, it is concluded that films had proper stability under storage temperatures. Additionally, competitiveness of active packaging may be achieved by designing films with high hydrophobicity. Developing water resistance, decreasing solubility and transmission rate. Water transmission rate (WTR) is a prominent characteristic which may be controlled by designing polymer matrices with fillers with proper number of hydrophilic groups (OH, NH) as observed in the studies [49]. The design of multilayered films is noteworthy for its ability to regulate moisture levels in fresh-cut fruit. The inner layer functions to control moisture, utilizing a hydrophilic-hydrophobic nature, while the outer layer provides a barrier against external moisture, exhibiting a hydrophobic nature [26]. In this case, this approach appears to be the optimal novel method for active packaging of fruits. It is versatile because can consider both high and low water-release fresh-cut fruits.

3.10. Limitations of Active Packaging

In contrast, many configurations suffer from low compatibility between polymer matrix and fillers. Main negative effects are presented in terms of mechanical performances. From them elongation at break is the most penalized property. Failure points and decreased mobility are the main causes of lack in flexibility. The properties of polymers can be enhanced through the judicious selection of an appropriate active material, the development of composites, and the utilization of crosslinking agents and plasticizers.

The results of all the studies indicated that the extension of fruit shelf life was a successful outcome. Nevertheless, the lack of standardization in the shelf-life testing methodology represents a significant concern. Further research must consider the type of fruit to be utilized, with conditions that can be standardized. Apples appear to be the optimal fruit for experimental shelf-life design, as they are susceptible to browning and microbial spoilage, which can be quantified to some extent.

Another limitation about fresh-cut fruit packaging literature is the inconsistency in storage conditions. It is essential that the relative humidity, temperature, and pH levels remain consistent between articles to mitigate the impact of external factors. It is imperative that only active packaging be identified as the source of the observed effect. This approach allows for a comparison of active packaging designs.

Similarly, the diversity in packaging formats, including the utilization of trays wrapped in the films, containers with lids of the films, bags, and direct wrapping, may influence the shelf life outcomes. The packaging format must consider variables such as the internal atmosphere and the physiological characteristics of the fruits. Thus, for one type of application, a containerized storage may be beneficial, whereas for another, direct wrapping may be preferable. However, this situation is a consequence of the lack of staging in fruit selection and/or application.

It seems to be good outcome from active packaging films that active molecules migrate to packed food. Almost all studies results indicate migration of components. But only two of them have fully characterized release kinetics. The migration may enhance even better the food preservation [46]. But it is mandatory to ensure consumers security. Likewise, for active packaging film design, materials must be supported by entities like the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) agency or the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).

4. Conclusions

Active packaging literature has become increasingly diverse. No research with common configurations or experimental designs has been reported. Many raw materials, active substances, and experimental designs have been employed. The lack of standardization makes it difficult to perform meta-analysis to disclose the better configurations. For this reason, there is still a long way to go in terms of research on packaging with active materials. In this article we disclose some performance of active packaging for fresh-cut fruits.

According to our findings, the use of polysaccharides in active packaging is commonly used, with chitosan being the most prominent polymer material. On the other hand, natural extracts are also potential sources of antioxidant and microbial activity. An adequate configuration of the polymer and active compound is one that contains the two raw materials, a polysaccharide as chitosan and a natural extract. These materials favor their economic, biocompatible, and biodegradable properties.

Both antioxidant and antibacterial activities have considerable advantages. Therefore, combining both activities may be the most prominent strategy. Studies on cut fruit have shown a significant decrease in enzymatic oxidation and microbial proliferation because of antioxidant and antibacterial active packaging. In general, the main benefit of active packaging in terms of shelf-life extension is between two and five days more than that of passive packaging.

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